

Value Addition in Mulberry: An Innovative Approach for Entrepreneurship opportunities in Rural Areas

Jyoti Thakur^{1*} and Kamlesh Bali¹

Division of Sericulture, SKUAST- Jammu -180009, Jammu and Kashmir - India

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Abstract

Mulberry (*Morus alba*) fruit and plant possess immense potential for value addition, offering innovative avenues for entrepreneurship, especially in rural areas. Traditionally associated with sericulture, mulberry's nutritional and medicinal properties have broadened its scope for diversified utilization. The fruit is rich in bioactive compounds such as anthocyanins, flavonoids, vitamins, and minerals, which contribute to its use in health-focused products like herbal tea, functional beverages, natural colorants, jams and syrups. Additionally, other parts of the plant, including leaves, bark and roots are utilized in traditional medicine and animal feed. By adopting small-scale, cost-effective processing techniques, rural communities can transform raw mulberry resources into marketable products, thus enhancing income, creating jobs and promoting sustainable development. This approach not only supports local economies but also encourages the use of indigenous resources for innovation in agri-business.

Corresponding author email: thakurj571@gmail.com

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Introduction

Mulberry cultivation is the cornerstone of sericulture, particularly in the production of mulberry silk, which is renowned for its superior quality and global market demand. While traditionally grown to feed silkworms, mulberry (genus *Morus*) offers a wide range of possibilities beyond its conventional use, presenting significant potential for value addition. These include the utilization of mulberry leaves, fruits, bark and roots in diverse industries such as food processing, pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and even textiles. In rural areas, especially those engaged in sericulture, value addition in mulberry can play a transformative role in promoting entrepreneurship, enhancing livelihoods, and driving local economic development (Ravikumar *et al.*, 2012). Mulberry leaves are rich in protein, vitamins, and bioactive compounds and are now being explored for their health benefits, including anti-diabetic, antioxidant, and

anti-inflammatory properties (Andallu and Varadacharyulu, 2007). Mulberry fruits are also gaining popularity for their nutritional and medicinal value, finding a place in juices, jams, wines and dietary supplements. Additionally, mulberry-based products such as leaf powder, tea, animal feed and herbal formulations are entering commercial markets, creating new opportunities for small and medium rural enterprises (Chattopadhyay *et al.*, 2013). With the growing consumer demand for natural and plant-based products, the scope for developing a mulberry-based value chain is expanding. This not only improves the profitability of existing sericulture activities but also enables diversification, reduces dependency on raw silk sales and promotes sustainable rural entrepreneurship. By integrating modern processing technologies, skill training and market linkages, value addition in mulberry can become a viable model for inclusive development in rural

economies (Devi and Das, 2016). This article aims to explore the various value-added applications of mulberry and assess their potential to foster entrepreneurship and self-reliance in rural communities.

Pictorial Flow chart of value added products of Mulberry (Sarkhel and Manvi, 2021)

Value Addition and Potential Uses of Mulberry Leaf

S.no.	Value addition of Mulberry leaf	Uses	References
1.	Mulberry Leaf Tea	Caffeine-free; acts as a laxative, relieves respiratory inflammation, supports liver/lung health and reduces blood sugar and cholesterol.	Tulasi and Viswanath (2013)
2.	Mulberry Leaf Juice and Culinary Uses	Promotes healthy skin; relieves throat irritation; used in foods like pakoda and dhokla; valued for natural sweetness and potential in food industry.	Iyengar <i>et al.</i> (2007)
3.	Medicinal Applications	Used in pharmaceuticals; provides antioxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-cancer, anti-obesity benefits; treats skin, GI, and neurological issues.	Sujathamma <i>et al.</i> (2013) and Sharma <i>et al.</i> (2020)
4.	Animal Feed	Nutrient-rich feed for livestock; superior to grasses and legumes; rich in carotene and vitamin A; enhances poultry health and egg production.	Sudo <i>et al.</i> (2000)
5.	Phytoremediation	Supports soil remediation; roots absorb nutrients and heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Cu); promotes ecological sustainability in moriculture	Zhou <i>et al.</i> (2015) and Ghosh <i>et al.</i> (2017)

Value addition of Mulberry Fruit

Mulberry is a flavorsome, delicate, and healthy dessert fruit, often referred to as a "third-generation fruit" due to its nutritional and therapeutic value. It is toxin-free and rich in phytochemicals such as anthocyanins, benzoic acids, flavonoids, flavonols, and hydroxycinnamic acids, all of which exhibit strong antioxidant properties (Yang *et al.*, 2016).

S.no.	Mulberry Component	Uses	References
1.	Mulberry Fruit	Mulberry fruit aids digestion, lowers cholesterol, regulates blood sugar and may help prevent	Singhal <i>et al.</i> (2010)

		cancer. It also boosts circulation, supports vision and promotes brain health.	
1.1	Mulberry Fruit Powder	Rich in anthocyanins; 100 mg powder from 10 g dried fruit; has anti-aging properties; supports heart health, cancer prevention, and aids carbohydrate digestion	Singhal <i>et al.</i> (2009)
1.2	Jam, Jellies, Syrup, Squash	High sugar content ideal for sweet products; used in medicine for flavor and color; helps manage hyperlipidemia, constipation, insomnia, and supports immunity.	Buhroo <i>et al.</i> (2018)
1.3	Natural Food Colorant	Rich in anthocyanins (cyanidin-3-glucoside and cyanidin-3-rutinoside); provides vibrant natural color; alternative to synthetic dyes with added health benefits	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2018)
1.4	Mulberry Fruit Tea	Traditional Chinese remedy; made from 'Sangshengao' mulberry paste; used to treat hearing and vision deficiencies.	Buhroo <i>et al.</i> (2018)
1.5	Mulberry Fruit wine	Rich in Vitamin C; made from overripe or sour fruit; popular in Europe, especially among women; believed to support heart and digestive health.	Alakbarov <i>et al.</i> (2000)
2.	Mulberry Branches, Wood, and Twigs	Used in cosmetics (hair lotions, moisturizers), furniture, fuel, sports goods (due to wood flexibility), baskets, and "artificial cotton" for textiles.	Wani <i>et al.</i> (2020)
3.	Mulberry Bark and Roots	Bark used for paper pulp and rope making; root bark used in traditional medicine (cough, asthma); ethanolic extract has anti-HIV potential (flavonoids like Moricin, Mulberrofuran D, G, K).	Buhroo <i>et al.</i> (2018); Wani <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Conclusion

Value addition in mulberry offers a transformative opportunity to stimulate rural entrepreneurship and sustainable development. By moving beyond traditional sericulture and exploring diverse applications such as mulberry-based food products, herbal supplements, cosmetics, and eco-friendly textiles, rural communities can tap into high-value

markets and increase income sources. This innovative approach not only enhances the economic viability of mulberry cultivation but also promotes skill development, local employment, and self-reliance. With the right support in terms of training, infrastructure, and market linkage, value-added mulberry products can become a cornerstone of rural entrepreneurship, fostering inclusive growth and reducing migration to urban areas.

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